

DESIGNING BENZIMIDAZOLE SCHIFF BASES: EXPLORING ANTIMICROBIAL POTENCY AND MOLECULAR DOCKING

Reshma P. T.*, Vidya K. M., Jisha Prems, Muhammed Nimraz, Shanid Roshan, Rasha Sithara

Dr Moopens College of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry Wayanad.

Article Received on 29 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 19 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 01 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18811566>

*Corresponding Author

Reshma P. T.

Dr Moopens College of Pharmacy,
Department of Pharmaceutical
Chemistry Wayanad.

How To Cite This Article: Reshma P. T.*, Vidya K. M., Jisha Prems, Muhammed Nimraz, Shanid Roshan, Rasha Sithara. (2026). Designing Benzimidazole Schiff Bases: Exploring Antimicrobial Potency and Molecular Docking. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(3), 791–798.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Benzimidazole Schiff bases have gained significant attention due to their broad spectrum of biological activities, particularly their antimicrobial properties. This study investigates the design, synthesis, and evaluation of novel benzimidazole Schiff base derivatives as potential antimicrobial agents. A series of Schiff bases were docked with specific proteins in order to find out the activity. Some of the Schiff bases are prepared by the condensation of benzimidazole with a range of aldehydes. The antimicrobial activities of these compounds were evaluated against bacterial strains, and their efficacy was compared to that of established antimicrobial agents. The results revealed varying degrees of antimicrobial activity, with some compounds exhibiting potent inhibitory effects on bacterial strains.

KEYWORDS: Schiff bases Benzimidazole nucleus Docking

INTRODUCTION

Benzimidazole Schiff base derivatives are an important class of benzoheterocycles which has received considerable attention in recent years. Benzimidazole is one of the most important key building blocks for a variety of biologically important molecules. The fact that benzimidazole nuclei is very important pharmacophore in modern drug discovery as well as in Medicinal chemistry and that benzimidazole residue is a constituent of vitamin B12 support their potential use as therapeutics.^[1]

These derivatives are of particular interest since some of them show antiepileptic activity, antidiabetic activity, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity, antitubercular activity, antihypertensive activity, anthelmenthic activity, antioxidant activity, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity, antiallergic, antiviral and anticancer activity, antiulcer activity.^[3]

Benzimidazoles are a type of heterocyclic aromatic organic molecule that has the key structural feature of six-membered benzene fused to the 4 and 5 positions of a five-membered imidazole ring structure. The hydrogen atom linked to nitrogen in the first position of the benzimidazole nucleus quickly tautomerizes, resulting in isomerization in the resultant molecules. The electron-rich nitrogen heterocycles of benzimidazole can quickly take or donate protons and allow the creation of different weak interactions, giving it an advantage in binding with a broad spectrum of therapeutic targets and demonstrating a wide range of pharmacological activity.

Molecular docking is a computer technique used in structure-based drug design to predict the interaction of small molecules with macromolecular targets. Molecular docking is a computer technique used in structure-based drug design to predict the interaction of small molecules with macromolecular targets. Analysis of bond conformations and binding free energy helps investigate biomolecular interactions and create therapeutic medicines.^[14]

In this work, the antimicrobial activity was determined by using agar plate method. The agar plate method is a widely used technique for evaluating the antimicrobial activity of various chemicals, plant extracts, antibiotics etc. this method involves preparing agar plates inoculated with microbial culture, then the antimicrobial agents are placed on this plates by either disc diffusion or well diffusion method. After incubation the zone of inhibition was measured. We use the microorganism "E. coli" in order to check the antimicrobial activity and the derivatives are compared using the standard amoxicillin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Synthesis of 2-(4-Aminophenyl)-1H-Benzimidazole

O-phenylenediamine (0.01mol) and 4-aminobenzoic acid (0.01mol) were refluxed with stirring in a magnetic stirrer for about 5 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled. The clear hot reaction mixture was filtered and allow to cool to 5⁰ C. Add ammonia solution. Filter the crystals, wash using water and dried. Yield (77%) as pale pink coloured solid. M.P 197⁰ C.

Preparation of Schiff bases

Place 2.09g (0.01 mole) Amino phenyl benzimidazole, 1.06g (0.01 mole) of benzaldehyde and 50ml ethanol in a 100 ml round bottom flask (RBF) attached to a reflux condenser introduce 1 ml glacial acetic acid drop by drop while the reaction mixture was warming, the content of the reaction mixture reflux on a water bath for 3h, the reaction mixture should ultimately be almost clear and homogenous, transfer the filtrate to a 100 ml wide-mouthed conical flask containing crushed ice.

DOCKING

Protein preparation

3D crystal structure of staph GyraseB 24KDa(PDB ID : 4URO) was downloaded from protein data bank. The protein for docking was prepared using the protein preparation wizard of Autodock. The missing side chains, back chains, and residues were updated. Water molecules present in the crystal structure were removed in the protein preparation process.

Ligand preparation

Benzimidazole derivatives are drawn by chemdraw. Using chemical tools the desired molecular structure is drawn.

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY EVALUATION BY SPREAD PLATE METHOD

As to identify the anti-microbial activity of ortho methoxy benzimidazole and para chloro benzimidazole of the sample was evaluated against E-coli. The agar plate method is a widely

used technique for evaluating the antimicrobial activity of substances. In this method, a test microorganism is uniformly spread on an agar plate, and wells or discs containing the test compound are placed on the surface. As the compound diffuses into the agar, it inhibits microbial growth in the surrounding area, forming a clear zone known as the zone of inhibition. The antimicrobial activity is assessed by measuring the diameter of this zone. Amoxicillin, a well-known broad-spectrum antibiotic, is often used as a standard reference to compare the effectiveness of test samples, providing a baseline for evaluating the relative potency of new or unknown antimicrobial agents. The zone of inhibition in an agar plate refers to the clear area surrounding an antimicrobial agent, such as an antibiotic disk, where bacterial growth has been prevented. This zone forms when the antimicrobial substance diffuses from the disk into the agar and inhibits the growth of susceptible microorganisms in the vicinity. The size of the zone of inhibition is an indicator of the effectiveness of the antimicrobial agent against the specific bacteria being tested; larger zones generally indicate greater sensitivity. This method, commonly used in the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion test, helps determine the susceptibility of bacteria to various antibiotics and guides appropriate treatment choices.

RESULTS

In this investigation, molecular docking studies were carried out using Autodock vina, and the resulting outcomes were compared with those of the standard ciprofloxacin. The ligands bind at the active site of the target receptor 4URO and the binding affinity were expressed as docking scores as given in Table. Among them, ortho methyl benzimidazole had the highest binding score of $-7.6 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, which is comparable to standard drug ciprofloxacin ($-8.9 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$).

Table Benzimidazole Schiff base derivatives with their docking score.

Compounds	PDB ID	Binding Affinity (Kcal/mol)
OMB	4uro	-7.6
PCB	4uro	-7.2
PMB	4uro	-7.0
4NB	4uro	-6.7
PFB	4uro	-6.5
CIPROFLOXACIN(STD)	4uro	-8.9

Figure 1: Docking.

Figure 2: Docking.

Table: Zone of inhibition for antimicrobial activity.

SAMPLE	ZONE OF INHIBITION
Ortho methoxy benzimidazole	25mm
Para chloro benzimidazole	23mm
Marketed Amoxycillin	26mm

Figure 3: Antimicrobial activity.

DISCUSSION

In this study, a molecular docking analysis was performed using ciprofloxacin as the standard reference drug and 4URO as the target ligand. The docking process aimed to identify novel compounds with superior binding affinities compared to ciprofloxacin. Based on docking results, a compound exhibiting a higher docking score was selected for synthesis. The synthesized compound was structurally characterized and subsequently evaluated for its antimicrobial potential. Antimicrobial activity was assessed using the agar plate diffusion method against selected bacterial strains.

CONCLUSION

The docking study revealed that the selected compound displayed a stronger binding affinity towards the 4URO target protein compared to the standard ciprofloxacin. These findings suggest that the synthesized compound could serve as a promising candidate for further development as a potent antimicrobial agent.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We place on record our thanks to the Management, Principal, Faculty members, Administrative staff, Lab staff, Library staff, Supporting staff and our dear classmates for their kind help during the period of our work.

REFERENCES

1. Marijana Hranjec *et al.*, synthesized novel Schiff bases related to benzimidazoles and tested on their antiproliferative activity. Compounds 18 and 19 exerted the strongest non specific antiproliferative effect on all cell lines and a concentration dependent effect on HeLa and MCF-7 cell lines at micro molar concentrations but simultaneously being highly cytotoxic on human fibroblasts as well.^[1]
2. L. Srikanth *et al.*, gave a context on the recently synthesized 2-substituted benzimidazole derivatives possessing important pharmacological activities have been high lighted.^[3]
3. Alam S.A.M.F, et al.synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives containing Schiff bases exhibiting antimicrobial activities.international journal of research studiesin biosciences., Jan. 1, 2017; 5(7).
4. Aarons SJ, Sutherland IW, Chakrabarty AM and Gallagher MP. A novel gene, algk, from the alginate biosynthetic cluster of pseudomonas aeruginosa. Microbiol, 1997; 143: 641–652.
5. Ates Z, AlagozKus C and Coban T. Synthesis and antioxidant properties of novel benzimidazoles containing substituted indole or 1, 1, 4, 4-tetramethyl-1, 2, 3, 4 – tetrahyddrnaphthalene fragments. J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem., 2005; 20: 325–331
6. Dhar D and Taploo CL (1982). Schiff bases and their application. J. Sci. Ind. Res. 41: 501–506 [4] Foks H, Pancechowska-Ksepko D, Kuzmierkiewicz W, Zwolska Z, Janowiec M and Augustynowicz-Kopec E. Synthesis and antibacterial activity of 1H-pyrazolo [3, 4-b] pyrazine and -pyridine derivatives. Farmaco., 2006; 42: 611–614.
7. Funrniss BS, Hannaford AJ, Smith PWG and TatchellAR. Aliphatic Compounds. In The

- Vogel's Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry, 5th ed. Dorling Kindersley Pvt. Ltd., India, Mahapatra DK, Bharti SK, editors. Medicinal Chemistry with Pharmaceutical Product Development. 1st ed. Apple Academic Press, 2008; 2019: 780–784.
8. Ward SE, Davis A, editors. The Handbook of Medicinal Chemistry. 2nd ed. Royal Society of Chemistry, 2023.
 9. Fonseca CSC. Medicines, the Haute Couture of Pharmacy: A Summer Camp for High School Students. *J Chem Educ*, 2025; 102(2): 593–8.
 10. Garrido A, Berthaut F, Manganoni J. Evaluation of the Use of a 360° Immersive Visit of the Organic Chemistry Practical Laboratory for Pharmacy Students. *J Chem Educ.*, 2024; 101(10): 4182–8.
 11. Antonelli L, Mattos RR, Victor MM, Cunha S. Beyond Medicine: Paracetamol as Reagent in Multicomponent Synthesis of 1,3 -Benzoxazine. *J Chem Educ.*, 2024; 101(9): 3891–7.
 12. Timmons SC, Kuzmanov A. Molecules in Medicine: A Week-Long Multidisciplinary Summer Camp for High School Students. *J Chem Educ.*, 2024; 101(4): 1544–50.
 13. Mitchell SL, McCourt JS, Nessel-Tollefson DJ, Kimball GL, Mikesell JN, Tollefson EJ, et al. What's in That Medicine: An Inquiry-Based Activity to Introduce Medicinally Active Natural Products and Metals. *J Chem Educ.*, 2023; 100(1): 410–4.
 14. Sinosh Skariyachan, et al., (2018) The majority of bacterial infections have developed to be highly resistant to a wide range of antimicrobials, posing a significant danger to the pharmaceutical sector. As a result, there is a pressing need to address the issue and test new antimicrobials.